

THE CRIMINALIZATION OF HOMOPHOBIA BY DECISION OF THE FEDERAL SUPREME COURT

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the criminalization of homophobia in Brazil through a decision by the Federal Supreme Court (STF). The methodology is based on the inductive method combined with bibliographical research. After analyzing the principle of criminal legality, which is recognized both in domestic and international law, it is found that only the law can establish crimes and the respective penalties, in compliance with the basic principle *nullum crimen sine lege*. Next, the recent jurisprudence of the Federal Supreme Court on the subject is analyzed, which equated the practice of homophobia, until then without a specific law, to the crime of racism, provided for in Law n° 7.716/1989. By proceeding in this way, the STF, according to the judicial theory (*mens iudicis*) proposed in this article, ended up creating a crime through jurisprudence, that is, it instituted a typical figure and the respective criminal sanction through the decision of its ministers. However, jurisprudence does not constitute the appropriate instrument to create crimes, as these are established only by law, being the result of the deliberation of the Legislative Branch, and not of the decision of ministers of the Supreme Court, under penalty of violating the principle *nullum crimen sine lege* and the prohibition of the use of analogy *in malam partem*.

Keywords: Homophobia. Creation of a crime by jurisprudence. Brazilian Supreme Court. *Mens Iudicis*.

Introduction

The study on the criminalization of homophobia in Brazil by decision of the Supreme Court is of notorious relevance, since it constitutes a basic principle, both in constitutional and criminal law, that only the law can create crimes and establish the respective sanctions.

The problem of this article is to analyze whether the decision of the Supreme Federal Court, through the use of analogy *in malam partem* or extensive interpretation, created the crime of homophobia through case law interpretation.

To this end, the work adopts the inductive method and bibliographical research. The investigation is divided into three axes: *i* – principle of criminal legality; *ii* - STF case law on the subject; and *iii* - creation of a crime by STF case law.

1. Principle of criminal legality

Nelson Hungria, when mentioning the historical evolution of the principle “*nullum crimen, nulla poena sine lege*”, reports that in the early Roman criminal law, formed as specific cases arose, punishment sine lege was not prohibited. This is because at the time of the government of judges, in conjunction with the people's court, several crimes and penalties were already predefined. However, the people's court could declare other conducts not previously considered as prohibited as punishable. Only later, when the people's court was replaced by the quaestiones process and criminal jurisdiction gradually passed to the jurisdiction of jurors, could a certain conduct only be punished if it was precisely incriminated. In other words, a reprehensible act could not be punished just because it deserved a sanction. Consequently, no crime without prior criminal law and no punishment without prior criminal law were allowed in Rome. Thus, it was established that the sole source of Criminal Law is the legal norm, and that Criminal Law does not exist outside of the written law. Criminal law is a closed system and cannot be replaced by judicial discretion, analogy, general principles of law or custom.⁴

Cesare Beccaria, in his classic work, already warned about the consequences of the primacy of the law, which is that “only laws can indicate the penalties for each crime and that the right to establish criminal laws can only belong to the legislator, who represents the entire society bound by a social contract”. The same author categorically stated that “the magistrate, who is part of this society, cannot justly apply to another participant in this society a penalty that is not established by law”.⁵

Likewise, Jiménez de Asúa teaches that the law is the immediate source of production and knowledge of criminal law, rejecting custom, general principles of law and analogy to create typical figures. This is because the law, in its formal sense, is the manifestation of the collective will be expressed through the constitutional bodies (Legislative and Executive Branches), published in accordance with the rules in force. Thus, criminal legalism prevails, that is, the law is the expression of criminal law and the necessary means of establishing crimes

⁴ HUNGRIA, Nelson; DOTTI, René Ariel. *Comentários ao Código Penal*. Volume I. Tomo I. 6ª ed. Rio de Janeiro: GZ Editora, 2017, p. 5 and 15.

⁵ BECCARIA, Cesare. *Dos delitos e das penas*. São Paulo: Martin Claret, 2000, p. 20.

and penalties. The characteristics of criminal law are: *i* – exclusivity (only the law creates crimes and establishes the respective sanctions); *ii* – mandatory (everyone must comply with it, both private individuals and the Public Authorities, with criminal law being a limit both on the conduct of citizens and on the State's right to punish); *iii* – unavoidable (the law can only be repealed by another); and *iv* – egalitarian (all people are subject to the punitive norm, as everyone is equal before the law).⁶

In Jescheck's lesson, criminal law is an expression of the Rule of Law, since, in respect of individual rights, all state acts that are harmful to citizens require the support of a criminal law, that is, they must be provided for in a regularly established legal norm. This measure is justified to the extent that the express determination of prohibited conduct in the law excludes the arbitrariness of the State, in addition to providing security and certainty to the legal system. As a consequence, criminal law plays a role of guarantee in the current State, since: *i* – it repeals customary law to create criminal types; *ii* – rejects the use of analogy and extensive interpretation to establish crimes and sanctions; *iii* – requires the determination of conduct prohibited by criminal law, in accordance with the principle *nullum crimen sine lege*.⁷

The principle of criminal legality – that “no crime exists without a prior law defining it” – is also enshrined in the perspective of International Law. In this sense, the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, proclaimed by the General Assembly of the United Nations on December 10, 1948, ensures that “No one shall be held guilty of any penal offence on account of any act or omission which did not constitute a penal offence, under national or international law, at the time when it was committed.” (art. 11, § 2).⁸ Likewise, the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights asserts: “No one shall be held guilty of any criminal offence on account of any act or omission which did not constitute a criminal offence, under national or international law, at the time when it was committed” (art. 15, 1).⁹

Equally, the American Convention on Human Rights enshrines the principle of criminal legality, so that “No one shall be convicted of any act or omission that did not constitute a criminal offense, under the applicable law, at the time it was committed. A heavier penalty shall

⁶ JIMÉNEZ DE ASÚA, Luis. *Tratado de Derecho Penal*. Tomo II. Filosofía y ley penal. 3ª Edición. Buenos Aires: Losada, 1964, p. 334-339.

⁷ JESCHECK, Hans-Heinrich. *Tratado de Derecho Penal*. Parte General. Cuarta Edición. Traducción de José Luis Manzanera Samaniego. Granada: Editorial Comares, 1993, p. 112-122.

⁸ UN. United Nations. Human Rights. *Universal Declaration of Human Rights*. Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/human-rights/universal-declaration/translations/english>

⁹ UN. United Nations. Human Rights. *International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights*. Available at: <https://www.ohchr.org/en/instruments-mechanisms/instruments/international-covenant-civil-and-political-rights>

not be imposed than the one that was applicable at the time the criminal offense was committed” (art. 9º, ACHR).^{10 11}

On the domestic front, the 1988 Federal Constitution, in the chapter on fundamental rights and guarantees, also establishes that “there is no crime without a prior law that defines it, nor punishment without prior legal imposition” (art. 5º, XXXIX, CF/1988).¹² The Brazilian Penal Code also guarantees the principle of criminal legality, stating that “there is no crime without a prior law that defines it. There is no punishment without prior legal imposition” (art. 1º, Decree-Law nº 2.848 of 1940).¹³

Thus, the principle of criminal legality is a postulate that is not only applicable within the scope of domestic law, but also stems from international standards, which the State must carefully observe. However, the Supreme Federal Court, when ruling on a case on the criminalization of homophobia, innovated by creating a typical figure not included in Law nº 7.716 of January 5, 1989, which defines crimes resulting from prejudice based on race or color. This is because the aforementioned law punishes crimes resulting from discrimination or prejudice based on race, color, ethnicity, religion or national origin (art. 1º, Law nº 7.716/1989).¹⁴ And the STF, through its case law, expanded the concept of the crime of racism to include the practice of homophobia, which is the subject of the next topic.

2. STF case law on the subject

The Federal Supreme Court (STF) has issued important rulings on the criminalization of homophobia. On June 13, 2019, the Court addressed the issue in the judgment of Warrant of Injunction nº 4.733, reported by Justice Edson Fachin. In this case, it was decided that the State has the duty to criminalize conduct that violates fundamental rights, since homophobia and transphobia constitutes unconstitutional discrimination, resulting in a legislative omission on

¹⁰ IACHR. Inter-American Commission on Human Rights. *American Convention on Human Rights*. Available at: <https://cidh.oas.org/Basicos/English/Basic3.American%20Convention.htm>

¹¹ Considering that the principle of legal reserve is also a guarantee provided for in international law, the agent who eventually practices discrimination against homosexuals and is convicted of the crime of racism (the defendant) may appeal to the Inter-American Court of Human Rights asking for the conviction of the Brazilian State for disrespecting the basic principle of criminal legality, that is, for criminally convicting him without the prior and unpostponable existence of a law promulgated by the Legislative Branch.

¹² BRAZIL. *Constituição da República Federativa do Brasil de 1988*. Presidência da República. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Constituicao/Constituicao.htm

¹³ BRAZIL. Decreto-Lei nº 2848, de 7 de dezembro de 1940. *Código Penal*. Presidência da República. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/decreto-lei/del2848compilado.htm

¹⁴ BRAZIL. Lei nº 7.716, de 5 de janeiro de 1989. *Define os crimes resultantes de preconceito de raça ou de cor*. Presidência da República. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L7716.htm

the part of the Brazilian National Congress. In the grounds for the ruling, it was considered that any type of discrimination, including discrimination based on people's sexual orientation or gender identity, violates the Democratic Rule of Law. This is because the right to equality, which is constitutional in scope, protects individuals against discrimination, naturally encompassing their gender identity and sexual orientation.¹⁵

The STF ruling also states that, in light of the international treaties to which Brazil is a party, the constitutional text contains a warrant of criminalize any and all discrimination that violates fundamental rights and freedoms. In this sense, the legislative omission by the National Congress in classifying discrimination based on sexual orientation or gender identity violates a minimum sense of justice by indicating that suffering and violence directed at gay, lesbian, bisexual, transgender or intersex people is acceptable, as if a person were not worthy of living on an equal footing with other individuals. However, the Constitution does not authorize tolerating the suffering that discrimination causes to its victims, and discrimination based on sexual orientation or gender identity, like any other form of discrimination, is harmful because it deprives people of the fair expectation that they will have equal value and respect. Based on these arguments, the Brazilian Supreme Court ruled in favor of the Warrant of Injunction to: *i* – recognize the unconstitutional delay of the National Congress and; *ii* – apply, until the National Congress comes to legislate on the matter, Law n° 7.716/89 in order to extend the classification provided for crimes resulting from discrimination or prejudice based on race, color, ethnicity, religion or national origin to discrimination based on sexual orientation or gender identity.¹⁶

Also on June 13, 2019, the Supreme Federal Court ruled on Direct Action of Unconstitutionality by Omission (ADO) n° 26/DF. In this case, the STF understood that homosexuals, transgender people and other members of the LGBTI+ community were exposed to serious violations of their fundamental rights due to the exceeding of a reasonable time to implement the constitutional warrants of criminalization established by the constitutional text of 1988 (CF, art. 5, items XLI and XLII). In this case, according to the aforementioned Court, the direct action of unconstitutionality by omission presents itself as an instrument to implement constitutional clauses frustrated in their effectiveness, due to the unjustifiable inertia of the Legislative Branch in creating a rule necessary to punish acts of discrimination practiced on the

¹⁵ STF. Supremo Tribunal Federal. Tribunal Pleno. *MI n° 4.733*. Rel. Min. Edson Fachin. Judgment at: 1306/2019. Available at: <https://jurisprudencia.stf.jus.br/pages/search/sjur432699/false>

¹⁶ STF. Supremo Tribunal Federal. Tribunal Pleno. *MI n° 4.733*. Rel. Min. Edson Fachin. Judgment at: 1306/2019. Available at: <https://jurisprudencia.stf.jus.br/pages/search/sjur432699/false>

basis of sexual orientation or gender identity. The STF called this phenomenon a “State of Unconstitutional Delay”, informing the National Congress of its delay in creating a law on the subject and, until such law is created, the Court decided to classify homophobic and transphobic practices, through interpretation in accordance with the Constitution, as racism provided for in Law n° 7.716/1989.¹⁷

Among the grounds for the decision, the STF equated homophobia with hate speech, and therefore homophobic and transphobic conduct is repulsive, and it is the state's duty to repress illegal practices against people who are members of the LGBTI+ group, as they are a vulnerable social group. Furthermore, the pursuit of happiness is an implicit constitutional derivation of the principle of human dignity, and the Supreme Federal Court must protect fundamental legal rights as a way of defending the Constitution. In the end, the STF ruled in favor of the request, with general effectiveness and binding effect, to consider racism in its social dimension as criminal acts subject to criminal repression. Thus, the Supreme Federal Court determined that, until a law is enacted by the National Congress, homophobic and transphobic behavior, real or supposed, that involves hateful aversion to someone's sexual orientation or gender identity, constitutes the crime of racism defined in Law n° 7.716/1989.¹⁸

3. Creation of a crime by STF jurisprudence

The Supreme Federal Court, despite its noble role of trying to protect the rights of the LGBTI+ population by establishing harsher criminal sanctions, ended up violating the principle of criminal legality. It is common knowledge that this principle states that only the law can define the conduct considered a crime and impose the respective criminal sanction. In other words, only the formal law, enacted by the National Congress, can create typical figures, and not a court, through an interpretative effort, having as its object a law that does not provide for homophobia in its text.

In fact, the Supreme Federal Court, on June 13, 2019, in a judgment of a Direct Action of Unconstitutionality by Omission (ADO n° 26/DF) and the Injunction Writ (MI n° 4.733), decided to usurp the function of the Legislative Branch by establishing the crime of homophobia through the use of the analogy *im malam partem*. This is because, based on the aforementioned

¹⁷ STF. Supremo Tribunal Federal. Tribunal Pleno – ADO 26/DF – Rel. Min. Celso de Mello – Judgment at: 13/06/2019. Available at: <https://jurisprudencia.stf.jus.br/pages/search/sjur433180/false>

¹⁸ STF. Supremo Tribunal Federal. Tribunal Pleno – ADO 26/DF – Rel. Min. Celso de Mello – Judgment at: 13/06/2019. Available at: <https://jurisprudencia.stf.jus.br/pages/search/sjur433180/false>

decision, the STF decided that, “until a law emanating from the National Congress is passed to implement the criminalization mandates defined in items XLI and XLII of art. 5 of the Constitution of the Republic, homophobic and transphobic behavior, real or supposed, that involves hateful aversion to someone's sexual orientation or gender identity, because they translate into expressions of racism, understood in its social dimension, are adjusted, by identity of reason and through typical adequacy, to the primary precepts of incrimination defined in Law n° 7.716, of 08/01/1989, also constituting, in the case of intentional homicide, a circumstance that qualifies it, because it configures a vile motive” (Penal Code, art. 121, § 2º, I, final part). (STF – Full Court – ADO 26/DF, Rel. Min. Celso de Mello – judgment 06/13/2019, thesis, first part).¹⁹

In view of this, there are several problems with the Supreme Federal Court's actions in this case: *i* – the Court is legislating (the Court's decision ends up legislating, because it creates a typical figure that did not exist until then in the Brazilian State); *ii* – the Court is establishing a crime through case law (the STF is completely moving away from the principle of legality, since homophobia does not have a specific criminal type, that is, the legislator did not create such a criminal hypothesis); *iii* – the Judiciary is replacing the National Congress in the function of creating laws, including those of a criminal nature; *iv* – the Court is concentrating in itself the function of formulating public policy, legislating and enforcing the law, that is, the functions of the Executive, the Legislative and the Judiciary; *v* – the Court clearly violates the principle of criminal legality, since only the law can create crimes, and not the understanding or case law of the Court; *vi* – the Court improperly uses the principle of analogy *in malam partem*, as this resource cannot be adopted to create a typical figure, as was done in this judgment; *vii* – there is no appeal in Brazil against the Supreme Court's decision, since it was adopted in the context of a Direct Action of Unconstitutionality by Omission, the result of which is unappealable, according to art. 26 with art. 12-H, § 2, Law n° 9.868/1999²⁰; in addition, the Supreme Federal Court is the last Court in the country, bindingly imposing its decisions; and *viii* – nevertheless, it is up to the interested parties, who are defendants or who are convicted of a crime of homophobia, to question the aforementioned decision of the STF as a matter of defense, in order to raise its non-application in view of the violation of the principle of criminal legality, as well as to provoke future re-discussion of the issue by the Court.

¹⁹ STF. Supremo Tribunal Federal. Tribunal Pleno. ADO 26/DF. Rel. Min. Celso de Mello. Judgment at: 13/06/2019. Available at: <https://jurisprudencia.stf.jus.br/pages/search/sjur433180/false>

²⁰ BRAZIL. Lei n° 9.868, de 10 de novembro de 1999. Dispõe sobre o processo e julgamento da ação direta de inconstitucionalidade e da ação declaratória de constitucionalidade perante o Supremo Tribunal Federal. Presidência da República. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/L9868.htm

It should also be mentioned that in the present case of criminalization of homophobia, a request was made for the enactment of a specific criminal incriminating norm, that is, the Supreme Court was asked to grant greater protection to homosexuals through the application of the racism law (Law nº 7.716/89).²¹ However, the Brazilian Penal Code already included generic protective norms that safeguard everyone (crimes of homicide, bodily harm, insult, defamation²², etc.). In other words, the Penal Code already protects the life, integrity, health and honor of individuals, and it is up to the Legislative Branch, if it deems it necessary, to create a specific crime to punish more severely crimes committed against a specific group of the population.

It should be noted that the legislator, in the exercise of its freedom of conformation, can establish crimes of discrimination and the corresponding sanctions for the various types of prejudice existing in society. For example, Law nº 7.716/1989, when defining crimes resulting from prejudice based on race or color, established that in the conduct of “injuring someone, offending their dignity or decorum, due to race, color, ethnicity or national origin”, the penalty provided is imprisonment of 2 (two) to 5 (five) years, and a fine (art. 2º-A). Already the Law nº 10.741/2003, when establishing the Statute of the Elderly, established that the conduct of “disdaining, humiliating, belittling or discriminating against an elderly person, for any reason” is subject to a prison sentence of 6 (six) months to 1 (one) year and a fine (art. 96, § 1).²³

That is, the legislator punishes discrimination based on race (with a sentence of 2 to 5 years of imprisonment) differently from discrimination based on age (with a sentence of 6 months to 1 year of imprisonment). In other words, because it is directed at different aspects of the person (age or sexual orientation), the same discriminatory conduct is punished with different severity under criminal law. And the Supreme Federal Court, through its interpretation, equated homophobic discrimination with racist discrimination (Law nº 7.716/1989), and not

²¹ Pursuant to Law nº 7.716, of January 5, 1989, “crimes resulting from discrimination or prejudice based on race, color, ethnicity, religion or national origin will be punished” (art. 1º), the maximum penalties for which are imprisonment from 2 (two) to 5 (five) years and a fine.

²² The crime of simple homicide consists of killing someone, the penalty for which is imprisonment for six to twenty years. For qualified homicide, the penalty is imprisonment for twelve to thirty years (art. 121, caput and § 2, CP). In turn, the crime of simple bodily harm consists of offending the bodily integrity or health of another, with a prison sentence of three months to one year. If the bodily injury is serious, the penalty is imprisonment for one to five years, and if the injury is very serious, the penalty is imprisonment for two to eight years. The crime of insult consists of offending the dignity or decorum of another, the penalty for which is imprisonment for one to six months or a fine (art. 140, CP). Finally, the crime of defamation occurs when someone imputes an offensive fact to another person's reputation, the penalty for which is imprisonment of three months to one year and a fine (art. 139, CP). Decree-Law No. 2848, of December 7, 1940, which establishes the Brazilian Penal Code. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/decreto-lei/del2848compilado.htm

²³ BRAZIL. Lei nº 10.741, de 1º de outubro de 2003. *Dispõe sobre o Estatuto da Pessoa Idosa e dá outras providências.* Presidência da República. Available at: https://www.planalto.gov.br/ccivil_03/Leis/2003/L10.741compilado.htm

with the penalty provided for age discrimination, for example, which has a lesser penalty (Law nº 10.741/2003). Thus, there is a punitive selectivity on the part of the STF, and such choice belongs to the National Congress when formulating criminal policy, and not to the judges of the Supreme Court.

Thus, in the judgment of ADO nº 26/DF and in the MI nº 4.733, the STF adopted an expansive interpretation, attributing a non-existent and inapplicable meaning to the concept of “race” to include homosexuals. The Supreme Court instituted a new way of interpreting the law, which is the judicial theory (*mens iudicis*), in which the interpretation is based on the judge's intention, that is, it is rooted in the mind of the judge himself.²⁴ This is because the voluntarist or subjectivist theory (*mens legislatores*) aims to identify the legislator's intention when creating the law, whereas the objectivist theory (*mens legis*) aims to identify the will of the norm, the purpose it projects.²⁵

In the *mens iudicis* theory proposed here, the judge uses the entire dogmatic framework and principled grounds to justify the decision he or she seeks. In other words, it is not a matter of identifying the normative content of the law, but rather of making an argumentative effort that substantiates the expected outcome in decision (proceeding or inadmissible). In this case, the judge departs from the text of the law to include the content that seems most appropriate to him or her, that is, what he or she would like to include or what the law should provide for, but which was not included in the normative hypothesis of the legal text.

Conclusion

Recently, the Supreme Court included homophobia in the concept of “race” through a broad interpretation (increasing the legal scope) and extra-normative (content not provided for in the text of the law). In this sense, the STF delved into the content of the sanction, that is, it established that homophobia is a crime comparable to crimes of racism until the National Congress creates a specific law on the subject. Interestingly, homophobia was considered equivalent to the crime of racism, which carries a greater penalty, and not to the crime of

²⁴ The judicial theory (*mens iudicis*) is formulated by the author of this article in light of the of interpretative activity created by the Supreme Federal Court, which has moved away from seeking the intention of the legislator or the intention of the rule. In this case, the court seeks the interpretation that, according to its conception, is the most appropriate for solving the problem, that is, the one that, in its understanding, is the most correct – even if the text of the law does not provide for such a hypothesis. Thus, in order to achieve the desired result in the judicial decision, the court interprets the legal text with the *ultra legis* defect, that is, it ends up going far beyond what the rule provides for as criminal conduct.

²⁵ NEVES, Castanheira. A. *Metodologia Jurídica: Problemas Fundamentais*. Boletim da Faculdade de Direito. STVDIA IVRIDICA 1. Universidade de Coimbra: Coimbra Editora, 1993, p. 98.

discrimination against the elderly, which carries a less severe penalty. This fact demonstrates that the Supreme Court's ruling was selective in relation to the type of crime that should encompass the crime of homophobia and the respective penalty, that is, the court chose the most severe penalty to punish discrimination.

It is worth asking whether other types of discrimination that occur in society could also be included in the concept of “race” and, therefore, receive a more severe punishment. As an illustration, we can use the example of discrimination against obese people (fatphobia), political discrimination (due to the fact that the person has an affection for a certain ideological agenda), discrimination against the poor (aporophobia), discrimination against beggars and homeless people, discrimination against the unemployed (who are unable to support themselves and depend on financial assistance from others or the State), discrimination against illiterate people (who cannot read or write their own name), discrimination against drug users (who are commonly called “addicts”), discrimination against prostitutes (who are called impudent names because of their conduct), etc.

Given so many hypotheses, one wonders whether such discrimination can also be included in the concept of “racism” under Law n°. 7.716/89 and be punished more severely, as is the case with homophobia as defined by the Supreme Federal Court. And if this is not possible, what criteria is used in this differentiation? Why can the aforementioned rule be applied to sexual or gender discrimination, but not to other forms of discrimination practiced by society? And given the legislator’s omission, will these minority groups be left unprotected by a special law? And what can the Supreme Federal Court do about this?

Therefore, discrimination is a reprehensible act and must be punished, but in accordance with the current rules, as set forth in the law. To this end, it is up to the National Congress to establish the criminal types and corresponding penalties, and not the Judiciary Branch through its interpretation of the law. In other words, in the current legal system, the use of analogy *in malam partem* is not permitted, since criminal law is governed by the principle of strict legality (only the law can create a crime, not judicial interpretation), and the principle *nullum crimen sine lege*, in addition to the fact that criminal types must be interpreted restrictively (*lex scripta and lex stricta*). Finally, case law is not a suitable means of creating crimes, since these are established only by law, which is drafted by legitimately elected representatives of the people, and not by judges in their judicial decisions.

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